

Synthesis of Formylcarbazole Derivatives and Acetylcarbazole

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Methyl derivatives of 1-hydroxy-2-formylcarbazole (3a-c) and 2-acetylcarbazole (6) have been synthesised from readily accessible carbazole units, as synthons for the synthesis of pyridocarbazole derivatives linked with anticancer activity.

CARBAZOLE 2- and 3-carboxy derivatives have been extensively used¹ for the synthesis of anticancer alkaloids ellipticine, and olivacine as well as of other pyrido[4,3-*b*]carbazole derivatives. The same intermediates can also yield pyrano[2,3-*b*]- and pyrido[3,4-*b*]carbazole framework. The formyl- and acetyl-carbazoles are by far the most useful synthons for the synthesis of condensed carbazole heterocycles. The present work describes the synthesis of 6-, 7- and 8-methyl derivatives of 1-hydroxy-2-formylcarbazole (3a-c) from the corresponding methyl derivatives of 1-hydroxycarbazole (1a-c)² by formylation, and of 2-acetylcarbazole from 1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocarbazole by acetylation and subsequent aromatisation.

Joshi and Rane³ formylated 2-hydroxycarbazole using Vilsmeier-Haack reagent to obtain 1- and 3-formyl derivatives in poor yield. 1,2,3,4-Tetrahydrocarbazole when heated with *N,N*-diethylformamide-phosphorous oxychloride, gave *N*-formyl derivative⁴; Joshi *et al*⁵ isolated only the *N*-formyl derivative when 2-hydroxycarbazole was reacted with *N*-methylformanilide and phosphorous oxychloride. In the present case (Scheme 1), when 1-hydroxycarbazole derivatives (1a-c) were formylated with DMF-POCl₃, three products were observed by tlc. The reaction mixture on hydrolysis with aqueous sodium hydroxide furnished only the reactant back, showing the failure of C-formylation.

Scheme 1

However, in the case of 1-hydroxy-7-methylcarbazole (1b) the *N*-formyl product, *viz.* *N*-formyl-1-hydroxy-7-methylcarbazole (2), m.p. 174-76°, could be isolated after silica gel chromatography.

C-Formylated products of 1-hydroxycarbazole derivatives were obtained by using *N*-methylformanilide and phosphorous oxychloride. These were shown to be 2-formyl derivatives from their diagnostic uv spectra⁶⁻⁸. This is one of the most powerful attributes of the formyl group attached to carbazole frame that helped assignments of the formyl group in alkaloids, such as heptaphyllene, heptazoline and murrayacin. In the present case the uv spectra showed a marked resemblance to that of 2-formylcarbazole.

Additional support for this position comes from the pmr signal of the phenolic proton which appears significantly down-field ($\delta > 11.7$) due to the presence of adjacent carboxaldehyde group. The effect of vicinity of aldehyde function on *ortho*-hydroxy proton is also reflected in the low-field phenolic proton signals of heptaphyllene (δ 11.70) and heptazoline (δ 11.50). Thus, the structure of pyridocarbazole synthons have been unequivocally assigned as 6-, 7- and 8-methyl derivatives of 1-hydroxy-2-formylcarbazole (3a-c).

The tetrahydrocarbazole derivatives present interesting structural feature, in that one part is aromatic and selective changes can be brought about in either part of the molecule. Kametani and Yonemitju⁹ oxidised 1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocarbazole to 4-oxo derivative. In the present case it was thought worthwhile to acetylate 1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocarbazole and then aromatise the alicyclic part of the molecule directly or after functionalising the benzylic position 1 or 4. However, Friedel-Craft's acetylation with acetyl chloride or acetic anhydride in presence of aluminium chloride with various solvents gave discouraging results. At best, the desired acetyl derivative (5), m.p. 205-6°, was obtained in about 15% yield by using acetic

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anhydride and aluminium chloride in dichloromethane. The N—H stretching frequency of the product shifted to 3270 cm^{-1} compared to that of 1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocarbazole (3400 cm^{-1}). The most deshielded proton attributed to the proton *ortho* to the acetyl group appeared as a *meta*-coupled signal at δ 7.94, showing that acetyl group was present on C-6 or C-7. The other two aromatic protons showed up as a clear AB system at δ 7.70 and 7.44.

Scheme 2

To determine the position of acetyl group on the molecule the acetyl derivative of tetrahydrocarbazole was aromatised by 10% Pd/C in refluxing xylene. Two products were obtained, 2-acetylcarbazole (6), m.p. 228-29° (lit.¹⁰ 230-31°) in about 50% yield, and 2-ethylcarbazole (7), m.p. 219-20° (lit.¹¹ 210-20°) in lower yield. The latter (7) could however be synthesised in yields upto 70% from 5 by the action of 10% Pd/C in decalin at 200° in an evacuated sealed tube (Scheme 2).

As expected, 2-acetylcarbazole (6) showed in its uv absorption a marked similarity to the 2-formyl derivatives (3a-c) as well as to 2-formylcarbazole itself which shows λ_{max} (log ϵ) (EtOH) at 252 (4.53), 321 (4.40) and 372 (3.64) nm⁷. 2-Ethylcarbazole (7) exhibited uv absorption reminiscent of 2-methylcarbazole. 2-Acetylcarbazole was thus synthesised and characterised as yet another synthon for the synthesis of potential biologically active pyridocarbazole derivatives.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237-B grating spectrophotometer, λ_{max} (log ϵ) (EtOH) on a Varian Super Scan-3 UV-Visible spectrophotometer, and ¹H nmr on a Varian XL 100 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

1-Hydroxy-7-methylcarbazole-9-carboxaldehyde (2): To cold dimethylformamide (1.5 ml), phosphorous oxychloride (0.5 ml) was added dropwise and the mixture kept at 0° for 10-15 min. 1-Hydroxy-7-methylcarbazole⁹ (1; 0.1 g) was then added and heated for 4 h at 95-100°. The cooled reaction mixture was poured over ice and the solid separated was extracted with ether (3×8 ml). The residue was chromatographed over silica gel column. Benzene eluant yielded 2 (0.06 g, 52.5%), m.p. 174-6° (benzene-petroleum ether) (Found: C, 74.80; H,

4.98; N, 6.02. C₁₄H₁₁NO₂ requires C, 74.65; H, 4.92; N, 6.22%); ν_{max} (nujol) 350, 1685, 1650, 1465, 775 and 735 cm⁻¹; λ_{max} (log ϵ) (EtOH) 234 (4.57), 271 (4.19), 280 (4.19), 309 (3.78) and 321 nm (3.89); δ (CDCl₃) 2.56 (3H, s), 6.95 (1H, dd, *J* 6.2 Hz) 7.12 (4H, m), 7.76 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 9.34 (1H, s) and 10.60 (1H, s, ²H exchangeable).

1-Hydroxycarbazole-2-carboxaldehyde derivatives: A mixture of *N*-methylformanilide¹² (0.15 g) and phosphorous oxychloride (0.14 ml) was stirred at 10-15° for 0.5 h. 1-Hydroxycarbazole derivative (0.20 g) was added to the mixture and left overnight at room temperature under anhydrous condition. It was then decomposed by adding ice-cold water (10 ml) followed by aqueous sodium hydroxide (15%, 10 ml). After 3 h the reaction mixture was neutralised in cold with concentrated hydrochloric acid. Ether extraction and usual workup yielded the product (0.12-0.15 g) which was chromatographed over silica gel. Benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1) eluted the respective compounds (3a-e). Benzene elution gave the starting material (0.09-0.12 g).

1-Hydroxy-8-methylcarbazole-2-carboxaldehyde (3a): 1-Hydroxy-8-methylcarbazole⁹ was formylated as described above to yield the yellow compound 3a (0.021 g, 18.4%, based on 0.10 g recovery), m.p. 198-99° (benzene) (Found: C, 74.63; H, 5.25; N, 6.35. C₁₄H₁₁NO₂ requires C, 74.65; H, 4.92; N, 6.22%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3260-3210, 1660, 1630, 1510, 1465, 1305, 755 and 735 cm⁻¹; λ_{max} (log ϵ) (EtOH) 222 (4.17), 258 (4.73) and 328 nm (4.36); δ (CDCl₃) 2.60 (3H, s), 7.22 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.32 (1H, br d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.34 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.66 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.92 (1H, br d, *J* 8 Hz), 8.48 (1H, br s, ²H exchangeable), 10.00 (1H, s) and 11.82 (1H, s, ²H exchangeable).

1-Hydroxy-7-methylcarbazole-2-carboxaldehyde (3b): 1-Hydroxy-7-methylcarbazole⁹ (0.2 g) was formylated as before to obtain the yellow compound 3b, (0.012 g, 10%), m.p. 189-90° (benzene-petroleum ether) (Found: C, 74.39; H, 4.98; N, 6.41. C₁₄H₁₁NO₂ requires C, 74.65; H, 4.92; N, 6.22%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3400, 1665, 1605, 1590, 1470, 1380, 1270, 800, 740 and 725 cm⁻¹; λ_{max} (log ϵ) (EtOH) 221 (4.42), 258 (4.89) and 330 nm (4.68); δ (CDCl₃) 2.54 (3H, s), 7.08 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.28 (1H, s), 7.30 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.62 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.94 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 8.42 (1H, br s, ²H exchangeable), 9.98 (1H, s) and 11.76 (1H, s, ²H exchangeable).

1-Hydroxy-6-methylcarbazole-2-carboxaldehyde (3c): 1-Hydroxy-6-methylcarbazole⁹ (0.2 g) was formylated as before to obtain compound 3c (0.015 g, 11.9%) m.p. 202-4° (benzene-petroleum ether) (Found: C, 74.52; H, 5.23; N, 6.30. C₁₄H₁₁NO₂ requires C, 74.65; H, 4.92; N, 6.22%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3390, 1670, 1470, 1380, 800, 780 and 725 cm⁻¹; λ_{max} (log ϵ) (EtOH) 223 (4.31), 257 (4.70) and 3.25 nm (4.46); δ (CDCl₃) 2.54 (3H, s), 7.36 (3H, m), 7.64 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.86 (1H, br s),

8.52 (1H, br s, ^2H exchangeable), 10.04 (1H, s) and 11.76 (1H, s, ^2H exchangeable).

7-Acetyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocarbazole (5): To a cooled mixture of 1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocarbazole (4; 17.1 g), 1,2-dichloroethane (50 ml) and acetic anhydride (9.5 ml) was added anhydrous aluminium chloride (26.7 g) in portions at 0-5°. The mixture was kept in ice-bath for 1 h and at room temperature for 24 h. A mixture of ice (75 g) and hydrochloric acid (50 ml) was then added.

1,2-Dichloroethane was removed and the residual dark solid mass filtered. It was triturated with hot benzene, and the benzene solution washed with water, aqueous sodium bicarbonate and water successively. Removal of solvent after drying gave solid mass (12.5 g) to which cold acetone (10-12 ml) was added. The yellow insoluble residue was filtered and crystallised from acetone as needles (0.6 g, 16.7%), m.p. 205-6 (lit.¹³ 206-8°) (Found: C, 79.12; H, 7.28; N, 6.51. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}$ requires C, 78.84; H, 7.09; N, 6.57%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3270, 1650, 1615, 1455, 1300, 1250, 1115, 825 and 815 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (log ϵ) (EtOH) 238 (4.19), 264 (4.18), 313 (4.10) and 353 nm (4.03); δ (CDCl_3) 1.88 (4H, m), 2.72 (3H, s), 2.84 (4H, m), 7.44 (1H, d, J 8Hz), 7.70 (1H, dd, J 8, 2Hz), 7.94 (1H, d, J 2 Hz) and 8.02 (1H, s, ^2H exchangeable).

2-Acetylcarbazole (6): 7-Acetyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocarbazole (5; 0.22 g) and Pd/C (10%, 0.11g) were refluxed in xylene (10 ml) under oxygen-free anhydrous nitrogen atmosphere for 2.5 h. The cooled reaction mixture was filtered and Pd/C washed with hot methanol. The filtrate was concentrated and cooled to yield compound 6 (0.10 g, 46.3%), m.p. 228-29° (aqueous acetone) (lit.^{10,11} 230-31°) (Found: C, 80.65; H, 5.48; N, 6.53. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}$ requires C, 80.36; H, 5.30; N 6.69%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3310, 1665, 1600, 1445, 1220 and 750 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (log ϵ) (EtOH) 254 (4.51) and 317 nm (4.47); δ (CDCl_3) 2.86 (3H, s), 7.20-7.54 (3H, m), 7.86 (1H, dd, J 8, 2 Hz) and 8.08-8.18 (3H, m).

2-Ethylcarbazole (7): A mixture of 7-acetyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocarbazole (5; 0.11 g), Pd/C (10%, 0.05 g) and decalin (8 ml) was heated in an evacuated

sealed tube at 200-5°. After 2 h the cooled contents were filtered and Pd/C washed with hot methanol. The filtrate was concentrated and cooled to give compound 7 (0.07 g, 69.5%), m.p. 219-20° (benzene) (lit.¹¹ 218-20°) (Found: C, 85.92, H, 6.57; N, 7.25. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}$ requires C, 86.12; H, 6.71; N, 7.17%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3370, 1600, 1460, 1375, 1200, 745 and 725 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (log ϵ) (EtOH) 238 (4.65), 250 (4.43), 260 (4.31), 298 (4.25), 324 (3.99) and 336 nm (3.70); δ (CDCl_3) 1.32 (3H, t, J 8 Hz), 2.80 (2H, q, J 8Hz), 7.04 (1H, dd, J 8, 1 Hz), 7.16 (1H, d, J 1Hz), 7.32 (3H, m), 7.80 (1H, s, ^2H exchangeable), 7.92 (1H, d, J 8Hz) and 8.00 (1H, d, J 8Hz).

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